

Deliverable D4.1

Notebooks and algorithms repository (accessible from the AI4Life website)

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BMZ	BioImage Model Zoo
D	Deliverable
DL	Deep Learning
ML	Machine Learning
PU	Public
RI	Research Infrastructure
v	Version
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

The AI4Life project aims to democratise modern Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods for biological imaging, building bridges between life sciences and computer vision researchers that can expand the reach of cutting-edge techniques. The aim of Work Package 4 (WP4) is to develop contributor services to help method developers and advanced image analysts integrate their deep-learning-based algorithms into the Biolmage Model Zoo (BMZ), the central project of AI4Life.

This deliverable (D4.1) presents the standard interface developed within the project to streamline the capacity to contribute, create, reuse and execute bioimage analysis machine-learning algorithms as documented in their source code. This standard is given in the form of a generalisable deep learning (DL) model format defined within the Biolmage Model Zoo and the corresponding software tools developed to consume, interact and write such a format in Java and Python, the two main programmatic languages for bioimage analysis. Additionally, an open-source platform – ZeroCostDL4Mic, a community partner of the Biolmage Model Zoo – offers a wide variety of user-friendly Jupyter Notebooks that enable non-expert users to interact with the AI4Life content. These notebooks help users finetune BMZ-compatible models and are findable and accessible through the Biolmage Model Zoo platform.

1. Introduction

The AI4Life project is part of the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, led by the project coordinator Euro-BioImaging and participated by ten partners, four of them being European Research Infrastructures themselves. The project started in September 2022 and will continue until September 2025.

AI4Life aims at bringing state-of-the-art AI-based image analysis to life scientists by establishing and supporting innovative services that target both researchers in the life sciences and computational methods developers in the AI and computer vision fields.

WP4 focuses on 'Contributor Services' and contributes to Objectives 1–3 and 5 of AI4Life:

- Objective 1: Democratised availability of AI-based image analysis methods as a FAIR service accessible through the AI4Life service landscape and computationally powered by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) infrastructure.
- Objective 2: Establish standards for the submission, storage and FAIR access of reference data, reference annotations (ground-truth), trained AI models, and trainable AI methods.

- Objective 3: Simple model deployment, sharing, and dissemination of AI-based methods as a new developer-facing service of the [BioImage Model Zoo \(BMZ\)](#).
- Objective 5: Empower common image analysis platforms with AI tools.

To do so, four different tasks were defined:

- Task 4.1 Establish containerization structure and services.
- Task 4.2 Easy development and deployment of new methods
- Task 4.3 Enable Human-in-loop BioImage Model Zoo workflow.
- Task 4.4 Continuous integration services (Automated testing).
- Task 4.5 Implement data sharing and protection guidelines.

This first deliverable (D4.1) focuses on Task 4.2 and 4.3 by providing a repository of notebooks and algorithms that enable the interaction (programmatic and in a user-friendly manner) with the BioImage Model Zoo content (the central repository to interconnect the tools related to the AI models and methods).

In this document, we describe this repository and how users can browse and exploit it.

1.1. Components of AI4Life involved in Contributor Services

The BioImage Model Zoo is the central point for interaction with AI-trained models and methods. It establishes a user-friendly space to search and launch models, methods, notebooks and even find datasets to train new models.

When an open-source and easy-to-use software for bioimage analysis is able to generate or consume models from the BioImage Model Zoo, it can automatically become a community partner of the Zoo. For this, the BioImage Model Zoo has its model specifications (i.e., a model format), which are agnostic to the task to perform or the deep learning model architecture. To facilitate compatibility with the model specifications and cross-compatibility among tools, two libraries have been developed, both in Java (JDLL) and Python (bioimageio.core), which are the main languages used to program bioimage analysis software.

At the moment, 6 bioimage analysis software tools can consume the models in the Zoo and have become community partners: 3 Java-based software (deepImageJ, deepIcy and QuPath) and 3 Python-based (Ilastik, StarDist and ZeroCostDL4Mic). StarDist and ZeroCostDL4Mic are also meant to train deep learning models and use the bioimageio.core library to export their models following the BioImageIO specifications (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the components of the Biolmage Model Zoo. The bioimageio.core package for Python provides deep learning model developers with a programmatic tool to easily export their trained models into a Biolmage Model Zoo compatible format and upload them into the Zoo. The Community Partners of the Biolmage Model Zoo are user-friendly tools for the consumption, training and production of deep learning models that provide easy access to these models and let non-experts deploy them. All these Community Partners are either Java- or Python-based software that became compatible with the Biolmage Model Zoo thanks to the integration of JDLL or bioimageio.core packages, which are backend tools for the consumption and export of the Biolmage Model Zoo format.

2. Description of work

2.1 Online distribution and accessibility to notebooks and algorithms

The new tools developed within WP4 are directly distributed through the BMZ, and the algorithms live in the Biolmage.IO GitHub community.

The BMZ is directly accessible through the AI4Life webpage. Also, the ZeroCostDL4Mic platform is accessible through both the AI4Life website and the BMZ (see Figures 2 and 3).

Figure 2. The Biolmage Model Zoo website. The website makes Biolmage.IO models findable and accessible. Each of the community partners is displayed, and its content, such as compatible models or user-friendly notebooks, is also accessible through the website.

Figure 3. Open-source and user-friendly notebooks are searchable and accessible through the Biolmage Model Zoo (<https://bioimage.io/#/?type=application&tags=notebook>). Users can look for the

notebooks using keywords such as “segmentation” or “denoising” to find those notebooks that will allow training, evaluating, and using deep learning models for those tasks. By clicking on “Open in Colab” directly on each of the notebooks, users can directly interact with the notebooks in the browser using Google Cloud services. They can also access example annotated open datasets for each of the notebooks.

2.2 Software tools for the interaction with deep learning models

To allow developers to deploy, consume, export, and import [Biolmage Model Zoo](#) models directly or within their tools, two different packages are available:

- [Biolmage.IO Core library](#) (Python package).
- [Java deep learning library \(JDLL\)](#) (Java package).

These libraries provide a common backend for the current (i.e., ZeroCostDL4Mic, ilastik, deeplmagej, ImJoy, and deeplcy) and future community partners to adapt the standards defined by the Biolmage Model Zoo easily. Moreover, they establish the assessment and testing of the current continuous integrating system (Task 4.4) of new models, which ensures the correct functionality of models and methods in the user-friendly software tools compatible with the Biolmage Model Zoo.

These libraries are synchronized with the model standards defined in the Biolmage Model Zoo. Therefore, they provide an easy path for new software and method developers to quickly adopt such standards and disseminate their work among the life sciences community (see Figure 1).

2.3. Open source and user-friendly notebook platform to support the interaction with AI4Life

The Biolmage.IO Core library provides a series of [example notebooks](#) to guide newcomers in the deployment, consumption, export, and import of the models in the Biolmage Model Zoo.

We also took advantage of the infrastructure and collection of Jupyter notebooks already within ZeroCostDL4Mic to stimulate the contribution of new methods and models that can be connected with the Biolmage Model Zoo (Task 4.2). ZeroCostDL4Mic is an entry-level platform (located on a GitHub [repository](#)) with a collection of Jupyter Notebooks that follow an easy-to-use graphical user interface. Its main goal is to develop these Jupyter Notebooks in a self-explanatory manner so that users with little or no coding expertise are able to use deep learning networks with microscopy data quickly.

The most popular notebooks within the platform (i.e., 2D, 2D multilabel, 3D U-Nets, and StarDist 2D) enable the consumption of pre-trained models in the Biolmage Model Zoo and the export of new models trained with different datasets.; So, the users can quickly populate the model repository and become compatible with existing user-friendly tools (e.g., ilastik, deepImageJ) (Task 4.3). This connection is enabled by the BiolmageIO.Core Python library, which is described in the next section (see Figure 4).

These exemplar notebooks constitute a template and standards for developers to create new user-friendly notebooks (Task 4.2) that can be directly connected with the Biolmage Model Zoo. These notebooks can also be distributed directly through the Biolmage Model Zoo or the ZeroCostDL4Mic platform, following the guidelines online.

Figure 4. Example of a user-friendly interactive cell in the 2D U-Net Multilable notebook of ZeroCostDL4Mic to export a documented model following the specifications of the Biolmage Model Zoo. This cell collects the metadata of the model provided by the researcher training the model, such as the name of the author, the affiliation, a human-readable description of what the model is expected to do, the license for the model, and optional information about the training data. With this, it automatically saves the model as a zip file that can afterwards be uploaded to the Biolmage Model Zoo or used in one of the community partners' software (see Figure 1).

3. Conclusion

The collection of notebooks within D4.1 and the ready-to-use libraries constitute a bridge between computer scientists developing AI methods and the FAIR ecosystem that we are building in AI4Life. These resources give developers and new contributors a chance to participate in this ecosystem easily, which is necessary to boost the integration of AI technologies into life-sciences research.

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